

Article

Examining Right to Education (RTE) as a Human Right: Act versus Implementation

Ms. Seema Dey *¹

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8286823

Key Words: Right to Education as a Fundamental Right, Primary Education, Neighborhood School, Life Skill Learning, National Education Policy, RTE Act, Challenges for Universal Education.

Abstract

In the recent past there is considerable amount of debate regarding the bill 'Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act 2009'. It marks a historic moment for not only the children of India, but also the whole education system of the country. This Act serves as a corner stone to ensure that every child has his or her right as an entitlement to get an enrolment in elementary education. It is a constitutional mandate for the state to provide primary education to all the children. In this scenario, this paper tries to examine the RTE in the domain of education as a system, with an analytical discussion on the education policy in general and right to education in particular. The view expressed by the author is the reflection as an academician who is involved in school teaching over two decades.

Introduction

According to Prof. Radhakrishnan, the former President of India, education is the process which brings transformation in the heart, changes the mind and moulds the character of an

individual. It covers the entire process of social life by means of which individuals and social groups learn to develop consciously within, and for the benefit of, the national and international communities, the whole of their personal capacities, attitudes, aptitudes and knowledge, for the betterment of society. The essential objectives of education may vary according to the socio-cultural-political context of a nation concerned, but there is a growing consensus under present international human rights law that tolerance and respect for human rights are major characteristics of a civilized society.

Right to education is also a human right because of its intrinsic nature and is the only means for understanding and promoting peace, progress which also includes realizing other's human rights. Human Rights common to all humans as members of humanity. All humans being presumably born equal are logically entitled, equally to the human rights without any distinction of birth, sex, race, status, religion, language or nationality. Human rights reflect the concern for social justice, participatory democracy, sustainable development, spread of peace, preservation of ecosystem & growth with human face. Any compromise with violations of the same is not permissible in any form in any given civilized society. These rights which are non-negotiable, non-alienable, and indivisible and recognized an essential worth of a human being, are fundamental for the existence of individuals in a civil society.

Human rights covers the series of often-disparate rights and freedoms asserted by many to be universally accepted and essential prerequisites for people's enjoyment of life based on human dignity. Proponents of human rights regard them as being inherent, inalienable and universal. It is inherent in the sense that they are the birth right of all human beings and people enjoy them simply by virtue of their human existence and as such these rights are not granted to them by any superior or sovereign authority; inalienable in the sense that people cannot agree to give them up or it cannot be taken away from them; and universal in the sense that they do not just apply to

¹ 1 Independent Researcher, NBU, Siliguri, West Bengal

individual as 'citizens' or 'groups' but to all persons regardless of their group identities.

Need of Human Rights Based Education

Human rights are those rights which are basic in nature and entitled to every human being because of their humanness, irrespective of his nationality, place of residence, sex, national or ethnic origin, colour, religion, language, or any other criterion. Such rights would include right to life, equality before the law, freedom of expression, the right to work, right to social security, right to education, collective rights, such as the rights to development and self-determination, etc. Therefore as evident human rights are inseparable, interrelated and interdependent. The improvement of one right makes the progress of the others possible. Correspondingly, the denial of one right has negating affects on the others. The basic right that is protected by the term human right is 'right to life with dignity'. A human rights-based approach to education is therefore necessitated since it assures every child a quality education that respects and promotes her or his right to dignity with a space for optimum development.

Right to education is not only a human right in itself but also is quintessential for the exercise of all other human rights. A number of human rights treaties accepted and recognized internationally, identifies right to education as fundamental for development and social transformation, across the globe. For a successful application of rights-based education two changes need to take place: human rights must be at the core of education policies and the 'universal human rights obligation' in relation to 'the right to education' needs to be clearly defined. The objective of right-based education is to translate globally accepted human rights standards into national education plans, policy and course curriculum. There are three primary actors: the governments as duty-holders, the child as right-bearer and the parents as representatives. Obligations relevant to education are presented in the form of availability, accessibility, acceptability and adaptability and affordability.

Availability – that education is free and government-funded and that there is adequate infrastructure and trained teachers able to support education delivery.

Accessibility – that the system is non-discriminatory and accessible to all, and that positive steps are taken to include the most marginalised.

Acceptability – that the content of education is relevant, non-discriminatory and culturally appropriate, and of quality; that the school itself is safe and teachers are professional.

Adaptability – that education can evolve with the changing needs of society and contribute to challenging inequalities, such as gender discrimination, and that it can be adapted locally to suit specific contexts. At the same time, it can be also conducive and adoptive to the local environment- socio-cultural and natural.

Affordability

It is equally important to examine the affordability of the child/ family in terms of whatever education is provided to them. Affordability here not only in monetary terms, but also in terms of time, space, location, culture specific, need of the society/ community/ family and the education provided to them. Otherwise the whole effort will go in vain.

As a matter of fact when education is simply seen as a development goal, an increase in school enrolments from 30 per cent to 40 per cent is regarded as a success. However in a rights-based approach, this increase signifies continued denial of the right to education to the 60 per cent total children available, still outside of school. Once a goal becomes a human rights obligation, failure to meet agreed goals by specified means becomes a violation: in the human rights-based approach, governments are held accountable for their promises. People are not seen as 'beneficiaries' but as active 'participants' and 'holders of rights'.

A review of the literature on education and child rights

There is a growing literature on education and child rights. Among those who have studied education and child rights are Gose (Gose, 2002), Tomasevski, (Tomasevski, 2003) (Tomasevski, 2001) Agarwal, (Agarwal, 1983), etc.

Education as Human Right at Global Level

There are a large number of human rights problems, which cannot be solved unless the 'right to education' is addressed as the key to other human rights. The right to education is clearly acknowledged in the United Nations' Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), adopted in 1948, which states: "Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit." (Article 26). Apart from UDHR, right to education is affirmed, protected and promoted in numerous international human rights treaties, such as the following:

Convention on Discrimination in Respect of Employment and Occupation (1958)

The International Labour Organization (ILO)'s Convention Concerning Discrimination in Respect of Employment and Occupation declares as its aim the promotion of 'equality of opportunity and treatment in respect of employment and occupation, with a view to eliminating any discrimination in respect thereof', and calls upon education to assist in securing this. States are required to 'enact such legislation and to promote such educational programmes as may be calculated to secure the acceptance and observance of this policy'. (Article 3)

Convention against Discrimination in Education (1960)

UNESCO member states have adopted two treaties aimed at eliminating discrimination in education. These include the 1960 Convention against Discrimination in Education and the Protocol Instituting a Conciliation and Good Offices Commission to be responsible for seeking a settlement of any disputes which may arise between States Parties to the Convention against Discrimination in Education, which was adopted in 1962 and entered into force in 1968.

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966)

The main UN treaty on civil and political rights, the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, defines education as 'directed to the full development of the human personality and the sense of its dignity, and shall strengthen the respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall enable all persons to participate in a free society, promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, and all racial, ethnic or religious groups, and further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace.'(Article 13)

Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination Against Women (1979)

The Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) obliges state parties to take all appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women in order to ensure to them equal rights with men in the field of education and in particular to ensure, on the basis of equality of men and women.(Article 10)

Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) (Articles 28 and 29)

Articles 28 and 29 of the CRC deal with the right of the child to education. Article 28 is

similar to the provisions contained in ICESCR. In addition, it states that school discipline should be administered in a manner consistent with a child's human dignity. Article 29 stipulates that the education of the child shall be directed towards the development of the child's personality, talents, and mental and physical abilities to their fullest potential. The right to education has therefore long been recognized by these international treaties as encompassing not only access to educational provision, but also the obligation to eliminate discrimination at all levels of the educational system, to set minimum standards and to improve quality. India is a state party to the ICESCR, the CERD Convention, the CEDAW Convention and the Convention on the Rights of the Child.

Education as Human Right in the Indian Constitution:

The Founding Fathers of our Constitution were committed to the protection and promotion of human rights and incorporated the same as Fundamental Rights in Part III of our constitution. Part IV of our Constitution sets out Directive Principles of State Policy. They embody the goals and ideals for making India a true welfare state in the right sense. Directive Principles are not directly enforceable by any court but are nonetheless 'fundamental in the governance of our country'. At one stage of our constitutional development, fundamental rights (part-III) were given primacy over directive principles (part-IV) which were regarded as subordinate to fundamental rights. It was considered necessary to give as much importance to the positive obligations of the State as to the negative instructions to the state.

The Constitution of India aims at establishment of socialistic pattern of society having welfare orientation. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and several covenants as also in the Constitution of India, which proclaims 'dignity of individual' as a core value in its Preamble. In spite of all this, it is indeed very disheartening to know that even after sixty years of independence, millions of people in this country live in a state of abject poverty,

deprived of basic amenities of civic life, i.e. proper food, cloth, shelter needed for the survival of a human being. If we will consider education, employment, health as the criteria, then ratio goes up. Hence naturally the issue of compulsory primary education was not given much importance by the framers of the constitution, though it was perceived that over a period of time, state will take all the endeavors to make primary education free and compulsory to all. Reason being the state will look after primary education, health care, public distribution system and other necessary public services, as these are the characters of socialistic pattern of society, which otherwise is the one of the basic structure of our constitution.

Historical Background

Way back in the year 1911, Gopal Krishna Gokhale demanded that Indian people be conferred with the right to education and had even urged the Imperial Legislative Assembly for the same. However, after 100 long years only his dream of free and compulsory education has come true.

Mahatma Gandhi's idea of Nai Talim was based on the philosophy of learning of education integrated with basic skills of life, which would make the development of body and mind. It was experimented in various places, i.e., wards, Seva gram, Sabarmati Ashram etc. Similarly former president of India, Zakir Hussain's idea of basic education with vocational skills was aiming at giving a holistic idea of education to human being, which was similar to Gandhi's philosophy. At the same time, Rabindranath Tagore was of the opinion that education must be in consonance with nature, culture, dance, drama, song etc., which makes the learning process lovely and lively. Man will learn from his immediate surroundings, ecology, happenings of day to day life. In fact there were number of experiments carried out in our country for success of various types of learning system and education in various parts of the country. Some of them succeeded and many of them failed also. Subsequently the 86th Constitutional amendment making education a fundamental right was passed by Parliament in 2002. In the year 2009 a law to facilitate the

realization of the fundamental right to education was passed by the Parliament by way of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act (RTE). The right to education has finally become a fundamental right by giving effect to the Act on April 1, 2010.

The act mandates the Government to provide education to every child up to the eighth standard, free of cost, irrespective of class and gender or any other social criteria. The following are the main issues of the act:

Schools have to ensure proper infrastructure, which includes a playground, library, adequate number of classrooms, toilets, barrier free access for physically challenged children and drinking water facilities within three years.

75 percent members of the school management committees will comprise parents of the students who will monitor the functioning of the schools and utilization of grants.

The National Council for the Protection of Child Rights (NCPDR) shall monitor the implementation of the act, together with Commissions to be set up by the states.

Financial burdens will be shared between the Centre and States in the ratio of 55: 45 and 90: 10 for the North-Eastern States of India.

Private institutions have to reserve 25 percent of seats from children from weaker sections of society.

Neighborhood schools will be identified by a system of school mapping, and children of six and above who are not in schools will be identified by local authorities or school management committees.

All such schools are required to be recognized failing which they shall be penalized for up to Rs. 1 Lakh.

The Act also prohibits donation or capitation fees and no admission test or interview of the child or parent for admission.

Children, who have either dropped out from schools or have never been to any educational institution, will be enrolled in the schools with no school refusing admission to any child.

No child can be held back, expelled and required to pass the board examination till the completion of elementary education.

It also provides for adequate number of qualified teachers to maintain a ratio of one (1) teacher for every thirty (30) students.

The Act is not clear about the following:

1. A number of PILs have been filed by various private unaided and minority schools against the Act, contending that the Act violates their fundamental right guaranteed under Article 19(1) (g), 29 and 30 of the Indian Constitution. The matter has been placed before a Constitution Bench of the Supreme Court & yet to be finalized.
2. The fundamental right to free and compulsory education has been confined only to education from the age of 6 to 14 and does not provide for the fundamental right to education in the formative years through pre schooling (for children in the age group of 3-6) and beyond 14 years, even if the child happens to be in middle school level.
3. In terms of admission into all types of schools more particularly private schools on the ratio of 75% to 25% for the children's from the socio-economic backwards sections of society. However it is not clear about the admission procedure. What is the mechanism to choose those 25% students.
4. It is quiet silent on the rights of children with disability. It does not facilitate the education for children with disability. As per the Persons with Disability Act, 1995, the government should ensure that every child with a disability has access to free education in an appropriate environment till he attains the age of eighteen years and not just up to 14 years as provided under the RTE Act. This is contradictory to the RTE Act.

5. It encourages implementation of its provisions through Public Private Partnership (PPP) model but there is every possibility of the apprehension that might lead to privatization and commercialization of education, which is a reality in the present time.

Conclusion

The development journey of the newly independent country 'India' started with lot of initiatives, hopes and expectations in 1947. It was envisioned by the founding fathers of the constitution to have as socialistic pattern of society, where the role of the state in the development domain will be crucial. There was a paradigm shift in the domain of public policy, where equal opportunity was provided to the private players, particularly in post liberalization period. As a matter of fact, private sectors do not run on the basis of charity, rather on the principle of cost-benefit analysis. Though there is constant demand from the public sphere that in the social sector, particularly primary health, primary education, public transportation etc, and the state should play its role as it used to be. In that context, the right to education is a phenomenal development to address the inequities existing in the education system, particularly at primary level. The right to education is well protected both in international human rights instruments and in regional conventions and declarations. Although instruments use different wording with regard to the nature of education, there is a wide consensus that the core content of the 'right to education' implies that states must guarantee compulsory primary education free to all. In order to meet their obligations, states must offer a genuine right to all children to compulsory primary education by making it available, accessible to all the children of the country.

References

A Guide to the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993.

Statement of Mr. Justice Ranganath Mishra, First Chairperson of NHRC, at the Conference on "Human Rights and Changing Global Values at Edmonton, Canada, November 4, 1995.

Agarwal, H.O. (1983), Implementation of Human Rights Covenants with Special Reference to India, Kitab Mahal, Allahbad.

Bajwa, J.S. (1995), Human Rights in India: Implementations & Violations, Anmol Publications, New Delhi.

Baxi, Upendra (ed.) (1987), The Right to be Human, Lancer International, New Delhi.

Bobbi, Norberto (1996), The Age of Rights, Polity Press.

Cassese, A. (1990), Human Rights in a Changing World, Temple University Press, Philadelphia.

Claude, Richard Pierre & Weston, Burns H. (ed.) (1989), Human Rights in the World Community: Issues & Action, University of Pennsylvania Press, Philadelphia.

Crowford, James (ed.) (1995), The Right of Peoples, Oxford University Press, New York.

Elumalai & Deepthi S. Nair (2002). Human Rights Vis-a-Vis Right to Education in Indian Context: Problems and Issues.

European Convention on Human Rights, concluded: 4 November 1950, entered into force: 3 September 1953, ETS No. 5. Protocol No 1, concluded: 20 March 1952, entered into force: 18 May 1954, ETS No. 9.

Gose, Michal, (2002). The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, (Bellville: Community Law Centre, University of the Western Cape.

Planning Meeting: Research on child labour in South Asia, Jaipur, June 18, 2000 CUTS-CITEE, Jaipur, <http://www.cuts-international.org/linkages-Meeting-18.htm>

Sepúlveda, Magdalena, The Nature of the Obligations under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, School of Human Rights Research Series, Volume 18, (Antwerp: Intersentia, 2003).

Special Rapporteur on the right to education and UNESCO Asia and Pacific Regional Bureau for Education,

Manual on Rights-Based Education: Global Human Rights Requirements made Simple (Bangkok: UNESCO, 2004).

Tomasevski, Katarina, Education Denied: Costs and Remedies, (London & New York: Zed Books, 2003).

Tomasevski, Katarina, Human Rights Obligations: Making education available, accessible, acceptable and adaptable, Lund: Raoul Wallenberg Institute, 2001.